

Cymenes as Xylene-substitutes by Catalytic Conversion of Indian Turpentine Over Supported Chromia and Platinum

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Dehydrogenation of the constituents of Indian turpentine, viz., 3-carene, α -pinene and β -pinene to *p*- and *m*-cymenes has been investigated over chromia-alumina, chromia-alumina-potassium oxide and platinum-alumina catalysts in the vapour phase. Weak acidic alumina impregnated with low percentage of chromium is very effective in the conversion of 3-carene to *p*- and *m*-cymenes. Platinum-alumina, unlike chromia-alumina, develops its catalytic activity in the lower temperature regions. The proportion of cymenes is always more from 3-carene than from pinenes. The total cymene content varies with the operation variables. The ratio of *p*-cymene to *m*-cymene (*p/m*) from 3-carene remains almost constant in the range of 1.5-2.0. Isokinetic relationship for the dehydrogenation of 3-carene over chromia-alumina-potassium oxide has been arrived at with a correlation coefficient of 0.988 and a standard deviation of 1.49.

INDIAN turpentine, produced to the extent of 6000-9000 tons per annum¹, is an important raw material of commerce which has not been fully exploited in chemical processes. Indian turpentine, unlike that of the European origin, is poor in pinene content (25-30%) but is one of the richest in (+)-3-carene (55-65%). The importance of carene has not yet been realised and bulks of carene and carene rich cuts are used as solvents for paints and varnishes. Attempts were made²⁻⁴ to obtain good yield of *p*-cymene from 3-carene since *p*-cymene can be converted to camphor⁵ and *p*-cresol⁶ and can be oxidised to terephthalic acid⁷ which is a raw material for synthetic polyester. *m*-Cymene formed from 3-carene along with *p*-cymene is an equally important compound. Isophthalic acid, an oxidation product of *m*-cymene, is a fire and heat resistant ingredient of plastics.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of (i) alumina (alumina A) impregnated with varying percentage of chromium, (ii) chromia-alumina (alumina B) doped with different percentages of potassium and (iii) alumina (alumina B) containing different amounts of platinum, on the transformation of the constituents of Indian turpentine, viz., α -pinene, β -pinene and 3-carene to *p*- and *m*-cymenes in the vapour phase and to relate some of the results with the energy of activation of the catalysts. Isokinetic relationship was arrived at for the dehydrogenation of 3-carene over potassium promoted catalysts.

Experimental

Alumina: Alumina A was prepared from potassium aluminate according to the method of Selwood *et al*⁸.

Alumina B was prepared from aluminium isopropoxide using the method of Pines *et al*⁹.

Chromia-alumina:

Alumina A was impregnated¹⁰ with requisite volumes of chromium trioxide solution to give 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 14 and 18% chromium, and alumina B was impregnated with the same solution to give 6% chromium. The 6% chromia-isopropoxide alumina was doped with requisite volumes of potassium nitrate solution to give 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.3 and 4.7% potassium as K₂O.

Platinum-alumina:

Platinum-alumina catalysts were obtained¹¹ by adding calculated volumes of chloroplatinic acid in water to alumina B to give 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9 and 1.4 % platinum.

All catalysts were dried at 120° for 24 hr and activated at 500° for another 24 hr in a furnace. The activated catalysts were crushed, ground into powder and sieved, and the 40-60 mesh particles were selected for use. The catalyst was heated in the reactor at 500° for 8 hr and reduced at the same temp. with pure dry hydrogen. In the case of chromia catalysts they were again reduced prior to each run.

3-Carene and pinenes:

3-Carene and α -pinene were obtained from top quality Indian turpentine by fractionation using a 152 cm glass column, packed with stainless steel helices, equivalent to 22 theoretical plates at 10 mm Hg. Since the concentration of β -pinene is too small in the oil, it was obtained from Fluka. The purity of the materials was checked by gas chromatography.

The reactions were carried out in a fixed bed flow type pyrex reactor. The reactant was passed through the catalyst bed using a constant feed-rate syringe pump that could be operated at different feed rates. The major products, viz., *p*- and *m*-cymenes were identified and quantitatively estimated using a gas chromatograph (AIMIL MK-II B) consisting of two metre column of carbowax on chromosorb. The minor products such as different menthadienes, menthenes, menthanes, etc., are not discussed here.

Results and Discussion

Chromia-alumina :

The formation of cymenes from 3-carene (which follows first order kinetics) and the energy of activation for their formation are plotted against chromium percentage (4-18%) in Fig. 1. The proportion of cymenes decreases while the energy of activation increases with increasing chromium content in the catalysts. The higher dehydrogenation activity of the catalysts containing low percentage of chromium is attributed to their better dispersion over the support. Increase of chromium content in the catalysts may lead to cluster formation as suggested by Selwood *et al*⁸ resulting in decreased formation of cymenes and consequent increase of the activation energy.

Fig. 1

The yield of cymenes over 6% chromia-alumina is 82.5% when alumina A is used (Fig. 1) and 65% when alumina B is used (Fig. 2). Alumina B was reported^{1,2} to contain strong acid sites that are capable of polymerising^{1,3} the unsaturates. The polymers and carbonaceous materials resulting from the side reactions may deposit on the active sites of the catalyst leading to a decline in its activity. The presence of such strong acid sites over alumina A is unlikely, since the residual potassium may preferentially neutralise the strong acid sites thereby

Fig. 2

preventing undesired side reaction, and this may explain the higher yields of cymenes.

With a view to confirm this presumption of coke formation and consequent decrease in catalytic activity of chromia-alumina from alumina B, this catalyst was doped with small amounts of potassium ions in stages and the dehydrogenation activity and energy of activation for these modified catalysts were determined for the dehydrogenation of 3-carene. The values are plotted against the percentage of potassium in Fig. 2. Initial additions of potassium upto 1.0% promote the activity of the catalyst and decrease the energy of activation. For instance, the cymene yield of 65% for a non-promoted sample attains 83% for a catalyst promoted with 1% potassium and the corresponding activation energy values are 22 and 16 kJ mole⁻¹.

Further additions of potassium have no beneficial effect. This enhances the activation energy considerably and brings down the cymene concentration in the product. Beyond the optimum concentration of 1%, potassium ions may block the active sites either physically or by chemical combination as pointed out by MacIver *et al*¹⁴. This makes it difficult for the carene molecules to approach the active sites and hence the cymene yield diminishes.

Platinum-alumina :

Platinum-alumina, employed extensively as a bifunctional catalyst for reforming of naphtha, has the following advantages over chromia-alumina: (i) platinum-alumina does not require reduction prior to catalysis, (ii) very small concentration of platinum is sufficient to bring about the reaction and (iii) platinum-alumina is active in the lower temp. regions (200-350°) thereby preventing the loss of catalytic activity due to sintering. The formation of cymenes from 3-carene, α -pinene and β -pinene over platinum-alumina catalyst is plotted against

the percentage of platinum in Fig. 3. The corresponding energies of activation are 9.2, 24.1 and 23.8 kJ mole⁻¹, respectively. The decrease in activity for dehydrogenation at higher concentration of platinum may be due to agglomeration. From among the three reactants the yield of cymenes is always higher from 3-carene than from pinenes (Fig. 3). Though the proportion of total cymene varies with the operating variables, the ratio of *p*-cymene to *m*-cymene (*p/m*) remains almost constant in the range of 1.5-2.0.

Fig. 3

Isokinetic relationship :

The isokinetic temperature, β , was calculated as the slope of the linear plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger (Fig. 4) for the dehydrogenation of 3-carene over potassium promoted chromia-alumina using the following isokinetic equation^{1,5}

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \beta \Delta S^\ddagger + \Delta H_0^\ddagger$$

The isokinetic relationship corresponding to the best fit equation is expressed by substituting the values of slope β and intercept ΔH_0^\ddagger which are obtained by least square method. The equation for the system is

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 1023 \Delta S^\ddagger + 311$$

with a correlation coefficient^{1,6} of 0.988 and the standard deviation is 1.49.

Fig. 4

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